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THE INFLUENCE OF THE LEVEL OF EDUCATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING PATIENTS AT THE DIABETES SCHOOL IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) leads to alarming clinical, social, financial, and public health issues with devastating long-term effects on the well-being, affecting quality of life including neuropathy, retinopathy, nephropathy, dementia, and cognitive problems.[1,2,3] Self-monitoring of blood sugar and apt self-care with effective metabolic regulation affect hypoglycemia, ketoacidosis, or microvascular and macrovascular complications.[3] DM prevalence has risen dramatically over the past 2 decades, with India being the major contributor. Global burden in 2011 was 8.3% (366.2 millions) compared to 4% in 1995 and is projected to rise to 551.9 million by 2030.[4,5].*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, insulin, hyperglycemia, metabolic regulation.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ УРОВНЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ В ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ШКОЛЕ ПРИ САХАРНОМ ДИАБЕТЕ 2 ТИПА

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Аннотация. Сахарный диабет (СД) приводит к тревожным клиническим, социальным, финансовым проблемам и проблемам общественного здравоохранения с разрушительными долгосрочными последствиями для благополучия, влияя на качество жизни, включая невропатию, ретинопатию, нефропатию, деменцию и когнитивные проблемы. [2,3] Самоконтроль уровня сахара в крови и правильный уход за собой с эффективной регуляцией обмена веществ влияют на гипогликемию, кетоацидоз или микро- и макрососудистые осложнения. [3] Распространенность СД резко возросла за последние два десятилетия, причем основной вклад в это внесла Индия. Глобальное бремя в 2011 году составило 8,3% (366,2 миллиона человек) по сравнению с 4% в 1995 году и, по прогнозам, к 2030 году вырастет до 551,9 миллиона человек. [4,5]

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет, инсулин, гипергликемия, метаболическая регуляция.

Introduction. However, our National Health Policy 2017 envisaged reducing premature mortality from diabetes and other non-communicable diseases to 25% by 2025.[6] There is a need to focus on preventive efforts with research on optimum choice of user-friendly test/s in the first contact care. Although glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C) does not require fasting and may be the best compromise, diagnosis and prognosis cannot be solely relied on HbA1C values that are affected in presence of different physiological and co-morbid conditions.[7,8,9,10] Diabetes education is considered an essential tool as its management largely depends on knowledge, motivation, and ability to pursue self-care in activities of daily living. Therefore, counseling and health education should be given paramount importance by the physicians even in their busy schedule including elaborate advice on lifestyle modifications and diet.[10,11,12,13] Although, evidences suggest that diabetics with more knowledge and motivated self-care help to achieve better glycemic control, there is difference of opinion on effectiveness of methods of health education and educational efforts to improve interventions are key components of effective treatment plan for DM.[14,15,16,17]. Health education is essential in resource poor settings such as ours, wherein DM pose great financial burden and calls for urgent participation of clinicians at all levels especially primary care physicians as they are usually the first care givers and come across known as well as recently detected diabetics. These patients can be imparted health education by primary care physicians to adopt healthy lifestyle practices, remain motivated for regular testing of glycemic status, and be aware of diabetic complications. The consequent changes in knowledge, attitude, and practices of diabetic patients are vital for achieving glycemic control and for preventing the development of complication of diabetes.

Objective: to assess the impact of the level of education on the effectiveness of teaching patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) at the diabetes school after 2 years.

Materials and methods: 188 patients (106 women 55.7%, 82 men 44.3%) aged 47-79 years (median (Me) – 61.4 years) with higher and secondary education, DM experience 12.4 years, BMI 30.5 \pm 0.72, attached to the State Medical Institution "Consultative and Diagnostic Center No6 DZM" of Moscow were examined (5 branches) and trained at the diabetes school in 2014. All patients were treated with oral hypoglycemic drugs. Compliance was assessed using a generally accepted standardized Russian-language Morisky-Green questionnaire. Statistical processing was carried out in the Statistica 7.0 program.

Results: according to the results of a survey of 188 patients with type 2 diabetes after 1 year after training, it was revealed that 105 (56%) patients did not follow the doctor's recommendations. The most common reasons for this were: forgetfulness of patients (44.6%), difficulty taking medications (21.8%), high treatment costs (26.7%). The analysis of the level of education of patients showed that among people with higher education, 48% fully comply with the recommendations, 10.8% partially and only 5.2% are incompetent. Among people with secondary education, 9.7% fully complied with the doctor's recommendations; 16% partially; 12.3% were incompetent. After 2 years, there was an increase in the group of patients who did not follow the doctor's recommendations to 124 (65.9%), of which forgetfulness was (54.4%); the complexity of taking drugs remained the same (21.8%); high costs decreased slightly to 24.8%. The analysis of the level of education revealed minor changes in patients with higher education: fully compliant 45%; partially -15.4%; incompetent 13.6%; with secondary education — fulfilling recommendations 7.1%; partially - 11.5%; not fulfilling 19.4%

Conclusions: assessment of the importance of the status of education in adherence to the implementation of medical recommendations for the treatment of diabetes mellitus demonstrated less compliance of persons with an average level of education. The differences in the indicators of this group were statistically significant compared to patients with higher and secondary specialized education. In this regard, it is necessary to motivate patients to undergo repeated group training at the diabetes school 1 time / 2 years.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод при резус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of*

- biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
 7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
 8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
 9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
 10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет И COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
 11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
 12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *Miasto Przyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
 13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin D deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
 14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
 15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmun tireoidit bilan kasallangan bemorlardagi funksional buzilishlarning differensial diagnostikasida qalqonsimon bez zichligini aniqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
 16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2. *I*. 2021;2(3):37-41.
 17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
 18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188

19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov AT, Norkulov A, Turamudov R, Zayniddinova D. Clinical observation of severe itsenko-cushing disease. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):549-556.
21. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdulkakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
22. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinova MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
23. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
24. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
25. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
26. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinova XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):341-345.
27. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
28. Ismoilov JA, Egamberdiyeva YK kizi, Mahmamuradova NN, Daminov AT. Family form of nephrogenic x-linked diabetes insuplius. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(4 SPECIAL):703-710.
29. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
30. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
31. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
32. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.

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